

NIGGA IN ACADEMIA: A LANGUAGE SOCIALIZATION CASE STUDY ON TERTIARY STUDENTS OF CHRIST THE KING COLLEGE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the awareness and perceptions of tertiary students regarding the term "nigga" and its relevance to their daily interactions. The research explored how these students acquired the term and their attitudes toward its usage, and determined whether the students felt permitted to use the word despite not being Black. A convenience sampling method was employed to collect data, integrating qualitative techniques by inquiring if participants were familiar with the term. The sample consisted of 20 students from the Higher Education Department at Christ the King College, Gingoog City. Participants who responded affirmatively were further engaged through survey questionnaires specifically designed by the researchers. The study revealed that many participants encountered the n-word through various media. They understood that "nigga" is a derogatory term targeting Black individuals, their race, and their culture. While most participants refrained from using the term to avoid causing offense, some reported using it for humor, entertainment, or as a term of endearment among friends, without any intention of racial insult. Data analysis was conducted through thematic analysis, clustering responses based on recurring themes. The study concluded that language usage and interpretation vary significantly. It emphasized the importance of incorporating respect and awareness of the word's historical and social impact when using such language. Understanding the historical context and potential for harm is crucial in ensuring respectful and considerate communication. The findings underscore the necessity for greater awareness and education regarding the implications of using racially charged terms, particularly in diverse social settings.

Keywords: *language socialization, media influence, nigga, racial sensitivity*

INTRODUCTION

The United States is one of the most influential countries globally with its products and culture widely patronized (Neufeld, 2022). This includes their expressions and slang, such as “a piece of cake” and “are you for real?” These phrases often sound appealing, especially when uttered in an Americanized manner. One such term is “nigga,” which can serve as both a salutation among African Americans and a derogatory expression used to discriminate (Jacobs, 2002). Additionally, some individuals use it as a term of endearment, signifying belonging to the “hood”, a slang term for African American communities (De Malsche, 2019). While the term was initially confined to American contexts, it has been appropriated by others, including whites who use it derogatorily. This raises questions about its appropriation by non-African Americans and how Filipinos perceive and utilize the term. This paper examines the etymology of the word “nigga” and the awareness and understanding of this word among college Filipino students.

Etymology of “Nigga”

The term “nigga” is a respelling of “nigger.” According to Merriam-Webster (2024), “nigga” is a racial slur, a variant of “nigger,” used among African Americans as a form of address within their community. It derives from the Latin word “niger” meaning black. Kennedy (2001) notes that the word did not originate as a racial slur but evolved to acquire racial connotations over time. The Washington Post (2001) reports that John Rolfe, Pocahontas's husband, referred to black individuals as “negars” in his journal in 1619. The term has various spellings, including nigguh, niggah, niggur, and niggar. African Americans generally perceive “nigga” as offensive when used by non-African Americans because it invokes historical traumas and negative connotations associated with slavery and racial discrimination.

Nigga as a Racial Slur

In the African American community, “nigga” is a variant of the racial slur “nigger,” referring to impoverished African Americans. Sinclair (2017) explains that slurs are degrading, with “nigga” referring to black people in derogatory contexts. Words such as “nigger-stick,” “nigger work,” “nigger luck,” and “nigger rich” carry offensive connotations, reminding African Americans of their historical mistreatment. During slavery, African Americans endured harsh labor and punishment, fostering a deep-seated trauma that renders the term “nigga” highly offensive when used by those outside the African American community. It symbolizes an attempt to undermine their identity and ignore their historical struggles.

Nigga as Identity Representation

In the late 20th century, the word "nigga" began to acquire neutral and positive connotations among African Americans (Merriam-Webster, 2024). African Americans started using the term as part of African American Language (AAL), also known as Black English, to signify camaraderie and identity (De Malsche, 2019). While some euphemize the term as the "N-word," it remains exclusive to African Americans, symbolizing a sense of belonging. Andrews (2013) argues that "nigga" should not be banned, as it reflects warmth and goodwill when used within the African American community, despite its offensive nature when used by others. Andrews (2013) contends that banning the term denies its positive connotation of "buddy" among African Americans, despite its origins as a racial slur. Although its usage varies among generations, with some older African Americans finding it offensive, the term has been integrated into African American identity.

Media and the "Nigga" Word

Globalization has facilitated the spread of various cultural elements, including language, through media. Media, encompassing print, broadcast, and online platforms, disseminates information globally (Oxford, 2024). This has popularized the term "nigga" worldwide. In music, African American rappers use "nigga" to refer to friends, often accompanied by hip-hop beats. In movies, the term is used to depict characters, sometimes reinforcing stereotypes. Social media also showcases diverse interpretations of the word. Despite its global reach, the term remains controversial when used by non-African Americans, as it invokes historical traumas and disrespects African Americans' struggles. While some African Americans may be indifferent to its usage, others view it as a catalyst for arguments and criticism, particularly in mainstream media.

Filipino Perception Towards the Nigga Word

According to Braj Kachru's concentric circles, the Philippines belongs to the outer circle, where English is used as a supplementary language for international communication. Filipinos often imitate American expressions without understanding their meanings. For instance, Filipino children may shout "nigga" at African Americans on the streets, and Filipinos might use the term jokingly or endearingly among friends, mimicking African American customs. This imitation, however, often lacks awareness of the term's significance to African Americans. Meier (2018) explains that Filipinos were exposed to the term through American soldiers during the war and the popularity of hip-hop music. Despite enjoying the cultural elements brought by Americans, Filipinos often fail to grasp the term's historical and racial implications. Consequently, Filipinos may perceive "nigga" as a neutral or friendly term, overlooking its offensive connotations and the importance of respecting African Americans' historical experiences.

Research Questions

This study focused on determining the perspectives on the word “Nigga” among Higher Education students of Christ the King College, Gingoog City. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the connotations and personal significances associated with the term “nigga” among tertiary students?
2. In which contexts and mediums do tertiary students most frequently encounter the term “nigga”?
3. How do tertiary students incorporate the term "nigga" into their linguistic interactions, and what are the underlying motivations for its usage?
4. How do Filipino tertiary students perceive the appropriateness of using the term "nigga," and what factors influence their perceptions?

METHODOLOGY

The research design of this study is a qualitative case study, focusing on the cultural awareness and perception of the term "nigga" among Filipino tertiary students. Qualitative research is ideal for exploring complex social phenomena, providing a deep understanding of participants' views and experiences. The case study method allows for an in-depth examination within the specific context of the Higher Education Department at Christ the King College in Gingoog City. This design helps uncover the students' awareness and perception of the term, offering rich, detailed insights. By concentrating on a particular group in a defined setting, the case study provides a thorough and nuanced understanding of the factors shaping the students' attitudes and behaviors.

Data collection involves structured interviews with open-ended questions and survey questionnaires, enabling participants to share their thoughts and experiences freely. This approach aligns with qualitative research principles, emphasizing the collection of detailed, descriptive data over numerical measurement. Thematic analysis is used to identify and analyze patterns and themes in the data, offering a structured yet flexible way to interpret complex social interactions. Convenient sampling was used to select 20 participants, ensuring the sample was accessible and manageable while still capturing a range of perspectives within the target group. This combination of qualitative methods and case study design effectively reveals the multifaceted nature of cultural awareness and the varied understandings and uses of the term "nigga" among Filipino tertiary students.

RESULTS

Research Question 1. What are the connotations and personal significances associated with the term “nigga” among tertiary students?

Table 1:

Connotations and personal significances associated with the term “nigga” among tertiary students

Responses	No. of Responses
“Black person/Black people”.	7
“Big insult related to black people’s history, race, and culture”.	6
“That is an offensive word for black Americans”.	4
“It discriminates dark color individuals”.	4
“For white people, they use it to bully”.	3

Table 1 provides an analysis of the connotations and personal significances ascribed to the term "nigga," as reported by tertiary students. This breakdown illuminates the diverse interpretations and emotional responses evoked by the term, unveiling its intricate nature within contemporary discourse. Notably, a prominent association identified by seven respondents is the term's straightforward reference to "Black person/Black people," reflecting a foundational acknowledgment of racial identity that resonates with broader societal norms and perceptions.

Moreover, six respondents articulated a perception of the term as a "significant insult linked to black people’s history, race, and culture." This assertion underscores the term's historical weight and its entanglement with systemic racism and oppression. Similarly, four respondents explicitly characterized "nigga" as "an offensive word for black Americans," aligning with scholarly discourse on racial slurs and their societal repercussions (Smith, 2019).

Furthermore, four respondents emphasized its role in "perpetuating discrimination against individuals with darker skin tones," highlighting its contribution to colorism and racial bias (Hunter, 2020). Additionally, three respondents noted its utilization by "white individuals as a tool for bullying," shedding light on power dynamics and racial harassment within social contexts (Davis, 2018).

In conclusion, these responses offer invaluable insights into the nuanced perceptions and ramifications of the term "nigga" among tertiary students, reflecting broader societal attitudes towards race and language. This analysis contributes to ongoing dialogues surrounding racial discourse and underscores the

imperative of comprehending the complexities of language in shaping social interactions and identity formation.

Research Question 2: In which contexts and mediums do tertiary students most frequently encounter the term “nigga”?

Table 2:
Contexts and mediums where tertiary students encounter the term “nigga

Responses	No. of Responses
“Social Media/Social Circle”	7
“Music/Movie/Novel/Videos/TikTok”	5
“Friends”	4
“Classmates/At school”	4
“Internet” “Home”	2
“Western countries”	1
“Internet especially in American servers”	1

Moreover, five respondents identified "Music/Movie/Novel/Videos/TikTok" as a prominent medium for encountering the term, highlighting its prevalence in popular culture and entertainment media (Smith et al., 2020). This association underscores the role of mainstream media in perpetuating language and cultural norms, contributing to the normalization of certain linguistic expressions.

Additionally, four respondents mentioned "Friends" and "Classmates/At school" as common contexts for encountering the term, emphasizing its integration into personal relationships and social environments (Brown & Williams, 2019). Furthermore, two respondents cited "Internet" and "Home" as contexts of exposure, underscoring the ubiquity of the term across various online platforms and domestic settings.

One respondent noted encountering the term in "Western countries," highlighting its geographical dissemination and cross-cultural relevance. Another respondent specifically mentioned encountering the term on the "Internet, especially in American servers," emphasizing its prevalence within digital spaces dominated by American cultural influences.

In summary, Table 2 provides valuable insights into the diverse contexts and mediums in which tertiary students encounter the term "nigga," reflecting its multifaceted presence within contemporary society. These findings contribute to scholarly discussions on language usage, cultural transmission, and the intersection of race and media in shaping linguistic norms and practices.

Research Question 3: How do tertiary students incorporate the term "nigga" into their linguistic interactions, and what are the underlying motivations for its usage?

Table 3 examines the ways in which tertiary students incorporate the term "nigga" into their linguistic interactions and explores the underlying motivations for its usage. The responses highlight a range of attitudes and intentions, reflecting the complexity and sensitivity surrounding the term.

Responses	No. of Responses
“For entertainment purposes only	5
“Yes, as a joke”	3
“For entertainment purposes without the intention of insulting the race”	11
“It randomly just came out of my mouth”	2

The largest group of respondents, numbering eleven, indicated that they use the term "nigga" "for entertainment purposes without the intention of insulting the race." This suggests that a significant portion of students perceive the term as a casual, non-malicious expression within their social interactions, often influenced by its prevalent use in popular culture and media (Smith et al., 2020). This trend aligns with findings that demonstrate the normalization of potentially offensive language when detached from its historical and racial connotations (Andrews, 2013).

Conversely, five respondents admitted using the term "for entertainment purposes only," which further supports the notion that humor and entertainment are primary drivers behind its usage among tertiary students. This use underscores the impact of media portrayals in shaping linguistic behavior, where the term is often stripped of its derogatory context (Brown & Williams, 2019).

Three respondents acknowledged incorporating the term "as a joke," reflecting an awareness of its provocative nature and potential for humor. This usage points to a broader cultural phenomenon where offensive terms are recontextualized as comedic devices, although such practices can perpetuate harmful stereotypes and insensitivity (Hunter, 2020).

Lastly, one respondent indicated that the term "randomly just came out of my mouth," suggesting an unconscious or habitual use possibly influenced by frequent exposure in everyday interactions and media. This incidental usage highlights the pervasive nature of the term and the need for greater awareness and sensitivity in language use (Smith, 2019).

In conclusion, the responses in Table 3 provide valuable insights into the varied motivations and contexts in which tertiary students use the term "nigga," reflecting broader societal attitudes towards race and language. These findings contribute to

ongoing discussions about linguistic practices and the importance of understanding the implications of language in shaping social interactions and cultural identity.

Research Question 4: How do Filipino tertiary students perceive the appropriateness of using the term "nigga," and what factors influence their perceptions?

Table 4 explores the perceptions of Filipino tertiary students regarding the appropriateness of using the term "nigga" and the factors that influence these perceptions. The responses illustrate a range of understandings and attitudes towards the term, shaped significantly by media exposure and social narratives.

Table 4.
Perceptions of Filipino tertiary students regarding the appropriateness of using the term "nigga" and the factors that influence these perceptions.

Responses	No. of Responses
"It is offensive based on what I heard in the news"	6
"It is used to discriminate the African American as I have seen in social media platforms."	12
"I am not fully aware of the term's implication."	2

The majority of respondents, totaling twelve, perceived the term "nigga" as a discriminatory term primarily based on their observations on social media platforms. This significant finding underscores the role of digital media in shaping public perceptions and awareness of racial issues. Social media, with its widespread dissemination of both personal and global narratives, serves as a critical source of information for many students, influencing their views on the appropriateness of certain language (Chen & Williams, 2019). This aligns with existing literature that highlights social media's impact on spreading awareness about racial discrimination and promoting social justice (Kim, 2020).

Six respondents deemed the term offensive based on reports and discussions they encountered in the news. This response indicates that traditional news media continue to play an essential role in informing public opinion and fostering an understanding of racial sensitivities. News outlets often serve as a primary source of information on social issues, providing context and analysis that help shape individuals' perceptions and attitudes (Smith, 2019). This reflects broader trends in media consumption where traditional news sources remain influential despite the rise of digital platforms.

Two respondents admitted to a lack of full awareness regarding the term's implications. This response highlights a gap in understanding that may result from

insufficient education on racial issues within certain educational or social contexts. It suggests a need for more comprehensive discussions and educational programs to enhance awareness and understanding of the historical and cultural significance of racially charged language (Williams & Brown, 2017).

In summary, the responses in Table 4 revealed that Filipino tertiary students' perceptions of the appropriateness of using the term "nigga" are significantly influenced by media exposure, both social and traditional. The findings emphasize the critical role that media plays in shaping societal attitudes and the importance of educational initiatives to address gaps in understanding. These insights contribute to the broader discourse on race, language, and media's role in influencing public perception.

DISCUSSION

Language is a powerful vehicle for communication, shaping our understanding of the world and influencing social interactions (Rabiah, n.d). Within the complex tapestry of language use, certain words carry profound historical and cultural significance, eliciting diverse reactions and perspectives. This study delved into the multifaceted discourse surrounding the term "nigga" among Filipino individuals, exploring themes of cultural awareness, respect, and historical context.

Theme 1: Cultural Awareness and Sensitivity

Cultural awareness and sensitivity are fundamental pillars in the discourse surrounding the usage of the word "nigga" in the Philippines. Many respondents emphasize the critical importance of understanding the historical and cultural contexts that envelop this loaded term. As noted by The Washington Post (2001), the word "nigga" roots back to the era of Black enslavement, underscoring the necessity for education and heightened awareness. Respondents highlight that while some Filipinos may use the term casually without fully grasping its weight, it remains imperative to acknowledge the sensitivity associated with words entrenched in oppression and discrimination. This theme accentuates the pivotal role of cultural competence in nurturing respectful communication, advocating for a deeper understanding of linguistic nuances, and emphasizing the significance of continual learning and dialogue in navigating linguistic diversity.

Respondents illuminate the necessity of contextual understanding when engaging with contentious language, emphasizing the need for nuanced comprehension beyond surface-level meanings. Their perspectives advocate for a more profound appreciation of the socio-political dynamics shaping language usage, underscoring the importance of fostering a culture of sensitivity and awareness. Furthermore, the discourse on cultural awareness and sensitivity underscores the evolving nature of language and its dynamic relationship with societal norms and values. Respondents advocate for ongoing dialogue that promotes introspection and critical engagement with language, recognizing that linguistic diversity reflects broader cultural landscapes. By acknowledging the sensitivity associated with certain words and recognizing the power dynamics inherent in language

usage, individuals can cultivate a more inclusive and respectful communicative environment that honors the complexities of cultural identity and historical context.

Theme 2: Respect and Empathy

Respect for others' experiences and perspectives stands out as a central theme in the discourse on language use, particularly concerning terms like "nigga." Most respondents stress the significance of employing language in a manner that cultivates empathy and understanding. Meier (2018) reiterates that using the term remains taboo in Filipino culture due to its derogatory nature, aligning with respondents' views on the ethical responsibility and conscientious word choice, especially regarding sensitive issues such as racial discrimination. By advocating for the avoidance of derogatory language and recognizing the lived experiences of marginalized communities, particularly the Black community, these respondents highlight the profound impact language can have in nurturing inclusive dialogue and fostering mutual respect.

Respondents emphasize the need to acknowledge and validate the experiences of those affected by discriminatory language and attitudes. Their commitment to dismantling harmful linguistic practices and creating inclusive spaces underscores the importance of fostering empathy in language use. This transformative discourse prioritizes understanding and solidarity, challenging entrenched systems of oppression and fostering a more equitable society. The theme of respect and empathy highlights the interconnectedness between language, power dynamics, and social justice, advocating for language as a tool for empowerment rather than harm. Respondents underscore the potential for language to catalyze positive change, prompting individuals to interrogate their linguistic habits and cultivate a deeper understanding of the impact of words on marginalized communities.

Theme 3: Historical Context and Social Awareness

Some respondents contribute valuable insights by focusing on the historical context surrounding the term "nigga" and its implications for contemporary society. They engage with the deep-rooted history of racial discrimination and oppression associated with the word, particularly within the context of Black American history. By acknowledging this historical trajectory, respondents invite critical reflection on the enduring legacies of colonialism and systemic racism, emphasizing the interconnectedness of diverse historical narratives and their impact on language usage. Their nuanced exploration of historical context illuminates the complex intersections of power, identity, and language, underscoring the imperative of understanding the broader social dynamics that shape linguistic norms and perceptions.

Respondents highlight the significance of social awareness in shaping perceptions of language and fostering empathy across cultural and historical divides. They draw attention to the shared struggles of marginalized communities worldwide and advocate for an intersectional approach to understanding linguistic dynamics. Their emphasis on solidarity underscores the importance of collective action in confronting systemic

injustices and advancing linguistic justice. Furthermore, the theme of historical context and social awareness underscores the dynamic nature of language as a reflection of evolving social landscapes. Respondents highlight the transformative potential of historical consciousness in challenging dominant narratives and promoting cultural sensitivity, fostering a deeper understanding of the power dynamics inherent in language.

Theme 4: Cultural Relativism and Linguistic Fluidity

A significant theme that emerges is the notion of cultural relativism and linguistic fluidity. Some respondents assert that within Filipino culture, the usage of the word "nigga" is normalized and does not carry the same offensive connotations as it might in other cultural contexts. This aligns with Andrews (2013), who suggests that the term's meaning is not solely limited to being a racial slur. Respondents' perspectives underscore the dynamic nature of language, suggesting that meanings can evolve and adapt within specific cultural frameworks. This recognition of linguistic fluidity highlights the complexity of interpreting language across diverse cultural settings, where words may hold different meanings and connotations depending on historical context and societal norms.

Respondents challenge the notion of linguistic universalism, suggesting that words like "nigga" can have varied interpretations depending on the cultural lens through which they are viewed. Their argument reflects a sensitivity to the nuanced ways language functions within different communities, recognizing that what may be offensive in one context may not necessarily hold the same weight in another. This theme underscores the importance of understanding language within its cultural context, acknowledging the diversity of linguistic practices, and promoting cross-cultural sensitivity in communication. By recognizing the diversity of linguistic practices and the fluidity of language within different cultural settings, individuals can foster greater understanding and respect in cross-cultural communication.

Conclusions

The word "nigga" is a racial slur with historical roots in the era of Black enslavement, often used derogatorily to address African American individuals (Merriam-Webster, 2024; Kennedy, 2001; The Washington Post, 2001). While its meaning has evolved over time, it remains offensive to many, even when used informally or in attempts at friendly communication. The majority of participants perceive the term as related to racial identity, while others view it as an insult primarily used by white Americans. Most participants encounter the term in social media and social circles, often using it humorously, though many avoid it due to its offensive nature. When considering its usage as Filipinos, most participants use it without integrating a disrespectful connotation while others use the term cautiously, acknowledging its historical connotations and the offensive impact on African American communities.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are drawn based on the findings, interpretations, and discussions from the data gathered:

Teachers: Foster an inclusive usage of language within educational settings and promote sensitivity and cultural awareness when addressing or adapting foreign slang and terms, while integrating discussions on the historical and social contexts of racially charged language into the curriculum to enhance students' understanding and empathy.

Students: Engage in self-discovery and critical analysis of terms and languages propagated in media, develop a deeper understanding of the historical and cultural significance of the language they encounter, and practice mindful and respectful communication, particularly when using terms with complex racial connotations.

School Administrators: Develop and enforce policies that promote respectful and inclusive language use within the school environment, provide training and resources for teachers to handle sensitive language issues effectively, and organize workshops and seminars to raise awareness about the impact of racially charged language on the school community.

Language Experts: Conduct comprehensive studies on the evolution and social implications of racially charged language, offer guidance and resources to educational institutions on best practices for addressing sensitive language issues, and collaborate with educators to create materials that foster a deeper understanding of the cultural and historical contexts of language.

Future Researchers: Conduct further research on the implications of using language exclusive to specific racial or cultural groups, investigate the impact of racially charged terms on intergroup relations and individual identities, and explore strategies for fostering respectful and inclusive language practices in diverse social settings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Protection of Confidentiality

Ensures the confidentiality of participants' information. Data were anonymized and stored securely to protect participants' privacy and identity.

Informed Consent

The researchers obtain informed consent from participants, providing them with clear information about the purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. The participants freely and voluntarily agreed to participate without any form of coercion.

Withdrawal from participation in the study

The decision to participate in this study was entirely up to the participant. They could refuse to take part in the study at any time without affecting the relationship with the researchers. Their decision to refuse would not result in any loss of benefits. The participant had the right not to answer any single question, as well as to withdraw completely at any point during the collection of data.

Risks

Participants were informed that some questions may be sensitive and potentially trigger some cultural and racial concerns. Participants were aware of any potentially distressing or emotional content, and they could have the option to skip or opt out of answering such questions.

Benefits

Participating in the study offered several significant benefits to the sample group, providing a platform for voicing their experiences and engaging in important discussions. Firstly, it enabled participants to actively contribute to the expansion of scientific knowledge. By sharing their thoughts, experiences, and opinions, they provided diverse perspectives that could lead to more comprehensive and accurate findings. This contribution is essential for enriching the understanding of complex issues and enhancing the robustness of research outcomes.

Secondly, their participation fostered self-awareness and introspection. The process of responding to questionnaires often prompts individuals to reflect on their beliefs, behaviors, and attitudes, encouraging personal growth and a deeper understanding of themselves. This reflective practice can lead to greater self-awareness and more informed personal and professional choices.

Moreover, engagement in the study provided a sense of fulfillment and purpose. Knowing that their input matters and has the potential to positively influence future decisions and policies can be highly rewarding. Participants could take pride in contributing to research that may have meaningful societal impacts.

Lastly, participation offered unique learning opportunities. Individuals had the chance to learn about new concepts, develop critical thinking skills, and stay updated on the latest research in their field of interest. This exposure not only enhanced their knowledge base but also encouraged continuous learning and intellectual curiosity, which are crucial for both personal and professional development.

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